

5:30 P.m. - 6:00 P.m. □

Everything you need to know about how to access technology services at the New School.

- MyNewSchool

NetID

New School Single Sign-On

Newcard

Non-Person Accounts

Password Change/Reset

VPN (Virtual Private Network) for Students

- Adobe Creative Cloud for Staff

- Banner

Hyperion

Perceptive

Tableau

- Google Drive

Google Sites

Office 365

Online Meeting Platforms

Zoom Web Conferencing

- Email Alias

- Gmail

Google Calendar

Google Groups

Mobile Devices (Email Setup)

- Large Scale/High Profile Events. Venue Leasing, Theatrical Performances

Screenings of Documentaries and Full Length Films (DCP, Blu Ray, DVD)

Small Scale Academic or Public Event without Specialized Technology

- Adobe Creative Cloud for Students

Apps Anywhere

AWS (Amazon Web Services)

Drop Box

Equipment Center

Printing

Qualtrics

Scanning

Technology Labs

VMware

Wireless Printing

- Fax Online

Jabber Softphone

Residence Hall Networks

Telephones

Voicemail

Wireless Network

- Employee Guides

- Laptop Choice Program

Network Share Drives

Printing (Office)

- 2-Step Login

Information Security Handbook

Information Security Policies and Standards

Secure File Transfer (Secure Send)

Two-Factor Authentication (Swivel PINsafe)

Virtual Private Network (VPN) for Faculty & Staff

- **Newcard Cash and Dining Dollars**

- Classroom Equipment Training

A to Z

Current Issues

All systems operational

Scheduled Maintenance

View scheduled maintenance

Report an issue

Help Contacts

- **IT Central**

IT Central

IT Central is currently operating remotely

Extended hours for the beginning of the Fall semester.

Hours:

7:45 a.m. - Midnight (Mon-Thurs)

7:45 a.m. - 9:00 p.m. (Fri)

Closed (Saturday)

Closed (Sunday)

Email: itcentral@newschool.edu

Submit an IT Service Request

646.909.4357 or dial HELP (4357) from a campus phone.

- Campus Card Services

Campus Card Services

Campus Card Service is currently operating remotely

Hours:

9:00 a.m. - 5:30 p.m. (Mon, Tue and Thurs)

9:00 a.m. - 6:00 p.m. (Wed)

9:00 a.m. - 4:30 p.m. (Fri)

Closed (Saturday and Sunday)

646-909-4472

Email: newcard@newschool.edu

- New School ZOOM Support Hotline

New School ZOOM Support Hotline

For immediate Zoom troubleshooting support call 646-909-9666 (ZOOM).

Hours:

8:00 a.m. - 9:00 p.m. (Mon-Fri)

10:00 a.m. - 6:00 p.m. (Sat)

Closed (Sunday)

The New School Zoom Hotline is for immediate troubleshooting support to assist faculty, students and staff navigate to a specific zoom meeting, assist with zoom meeting controls and escalate specific issues to additional teams, ready to assist getting online classes moving.

Zoombombings can be reported to the Zoom Hotline or via email at itcentral@newschool.edu.

- Events IT

Events IT

66 West 12th Street, Room 303

Hours:

8:00 a.m. - 10:00 p.m. (Mon - Fri)

9:00 a.m. - 5:00 p.m. (Saturday)

212.229.5300 x2310

Email: eventsit@newschool.edu

- Adobe Enterprise Customer Service

Adobe Enterprise Customer Service

ecs@adobe.com

www.adobe.com/in/company/contact.html

- Equipment Center

Equipment Center

55 West 13th Street, Room 102

Fall 2020

Please note changes to our regular operations

Hours:

September 14 - December 18, 2020

10:00 a.m. - 6:00 p.m. (Mon-Fri)

Closed September 7

Closed November [send fax by email](#) 25-30

646.909.4556

Email: eqc@newschool.edu

- AWS Customer Support

AWS Customer Support

For specific questions about the AWS Educate program or guidance on AWS services, contact AWS Customer Support.

- Parsons Paris

Parsons Paris

Student Lounge, 45 Rue Saint Roch

Hours:

11:30 a.m. - 12:30 p.m. / 5:30 p.m. - 6:00 p.m. (Mon - Thur)

11:30 a.m. - 12:30 p.m. (Fri)

Email Parsons Paris Adobe Creative Cloud support.